

Effect Of Self-Management Technique in Reducing Excessive Social Media Usage Among Federal University Students in Southern Nigeria

Prof. G. C. Unachukwu¹ & Iweanya, Emeka Nkem²

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

²Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5481732>

Abstract

The study was carried out to investigate the effect of self-management technique in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students in southern Nigeria. Two research questions and research hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a quasi- experimental pretest, posttest and control group research design. The population comprised of 928 first and second year federal university students from guidance and counselling department across the eight (8) federal universities in Southern Nigeria who offered guidance and counseling at the undergraduate level and sample size comprised of 65 first year and second year students from two federal universities in Nigeria who had the highest number of excessive social media users. The social media disorder scale (SMD) developed by Eijnden, Lemmen and Valkenburg (2016) was used to obtain data used in answering the research questions and testing the hypotheses. The null hypotheses were tested using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that self-management technique was effective in reducing students' excessive social media. The finding also showed that Self-management technique is more effective in reducing female students' excessive usage of social media. Based on the findings, this study therefore recommended that Self-management strategies and techniques should be adopted by students to help them monitor and observe their social media usage which would enable them control themselves when their online presence and activities are becoming problematic. This intervention will help students focus more on academic activities and be able to achieve academic excellence rather than while away most of their time on social media networks. The study further suggested for more studies to be conducted using the technique to checkmate excessive social media use in other schools and related organizations.

Key words: Effect, Self-Management, Technique, Social Media, Usage

Introduction

Nowadays, the advent of technology is quickly emerging before the eyes and undeniably, it takes a vital part in people's lives. One of the evidence of this is the development of the social media. The social media

provides instantaneous access to information at all times. With the evolution of these sites, it changes the way one communicates and how one finds and shares personal information, exchange ideas, feelings, photos and videos at overwhelming rate. Social media brought many positive implications to human life such as making the connection of millions of people from all over the world possible within few seconds. However, because of their limited capacity for self-regulation and susceptibility to peer pressure, students and adolescents are at great risk as they navigate and experiment with the social media.

The social media is a platform for people to discuss their issues and opinions. They are computer tools that allow people to share or exchange information, ideas, images, videos and even more with each other through a particular network or the other. It includes social networking sites and blogs where people can easily connect with each other and these sites have become a day to day routine for the people. The social media therefore has been defined as “the relatively inexpensive and widely accessible electronic tools that facilitate anyone to publish and access information, collaborate on a common effort, or build relationship” (Shabnoor & Tajinder, 2016).

Social media usage includes registering in a network and creating a profile which can be used for social or business interactions with other users in a virtual world. The use of social media and other electronic communication is expanding exponentially as the number of social media outlets, platforms and applications available continue to increase. Individuals use blogs, social networking sites, video sites, online chat rooms and forums to communicate both personally and professionally with others. Social media is an exciting and valuable tool when used wisely. The very nature of this medium, however, can pose a risk as it offers instantaneous posting opportunities that allow little time for reflective thought and carries the added burden that what is been posted on the social media can be implicating even when it has been long deleted (Ghulam, Yoseuf & Syed, 2014).

Furthermore, the social media is a complex network in which people design their own profile and become users. After that, they enlist other users in the profile and then begin to interact socially in a virtual world of social media and exchange information in a close network. Advancement in these technologies usually alter the learning technique of students. These individuals are often overly concerned about the social media and are driven by an uncontrollable urge to log on to and use the social media (Andreassen & Pallesen, 2014).

In line with the above, excessive social media use can be seen as the constant or re-occurring usage of various social media sites to the point where it begins to negatively affect an individual daily life routine like going late to work or missing classes in school just to spend more hours on facebook. Griffins, Kuss and Demetrovics (2014) viewed excessive social media use as the negative outcomes triggered by the excessive use of social media which may have a detrimental effect on the personal, social and/or professional lives of the users. Similarly, Wu, Cheung, Ku and Hung (2013) argued that obsessive Facebook users are those that have troubles in work, academic performance and interpersonal relationships as a result.

Recent research indicates that there are frequent online expressions of offline behaviours such as bullying, click-forming and sexual experimentation that have introduced problems such as cyber bullying, privacy issue and sexing (Kopecky, 2014). Students are also prone to getting addicted to these social media sites like Facebook, Myspace, Whatsapp, Instagram, Twitter, Wechat, LinkedIn, Snapchat, and Youtube and because of the lengthy hours they spend online, they also face concurrent sleep deprivation. The social media plays a large and influential decision making role in the global world economically, politically, socially and educationally. However, the use of these sites can either be a blessing or a curse as some people argue that it threatens the lives of teenagers. This is because they seem to get addicted to it especially students who spend more time online chatting and sharing pictures with friends than they spend reading their books and doing assignments given to them in school.

Social networking sites are increasingly important to the educational and social lives of university students and are becoming a part of their identity (Ahad & Lim, 2014). As these electronic and communication facilities allow people to catch each other anytime and anywhere, the social media becomes real life to them and as such, it becomes addictive. This addiction is specific to those referred to as digital citizens, which are the young people and largely students. Pamoukaghlian (2011) highlighted that the next decade will see the growth of new addiction related to all manner of social networking sites, especially the current king of the jungle; Facebook. Likewise, Cabral (2011), focusing on the social media as a reason behind this new addiction, pointed out that the major factor contributing to high usability of social media is that it connects people without boundaries, and as such, the social media basically becomes a template for the user who can then personalize its uses and productivity.

Furthermore, it was ascertained that teenagers operate these social sites for pleasurable activities rather than for academic success (Clark, Logan, Luckin, Mee & Oliver, 2009). Specific investigator brought into light that high school students operate these media only to strengthen their social dominance over the other users. Globally, teenagers get easily amused by the social media due to its advancements and the opportunity it gives them to reconnect with friends through various sites especially Facebook which is arguably the most popular social site among students (Meishar-Tal & Pieterse, 2012).

Moreover a survey carried out by Lenhart, Purcell, Smith and Zickuhr (2010) in India exposed that 24% of respondents uses social media on a daily basis and 52% have more than two profiles on different social media sites. It is estimated that 73% of teenagers prefer to interact on Facebook, 48% rely on Myspace and LinkedIn have a usage of 14% . There is a steep rise in the usage of social media sites by youngsters. However, a survey was conducted named parent and teen survey and 935 individuals participated in it in America. This shows that in 2006, 55% of teenagers were daily users of social media (The Nielsen Company, 2009). Observations conclude that the main purpose for the use of these social media sites were to remain in contact, and constant communication, and become influential on the social network by frequently visiting it.

Similarly, excessive social media use can be seen as the addiction to various social media platforms because it is easy to use and equally entertaining and it becomes a problem when it begins to interfere with daily life activities (Pamaoukaghion, 2010). Negative outcomes triggered by the excessive use of social media may have a detrimental effect on the personal, social, and/or professional lives of the users. Grifftins et al (2014) argued that obsessive Facebook users had troubles in work, academic performance and interpersonal relationships. Yet while social media has been lauded for its ability to connect people from all over the world, build friendships, support political causes, and even help people find work, it has also been blamed for a whole host of social problems. As it turns out, being so connected all the time comes with serious drawbacks. It can shorten attention spans, become addictive, lead to less diverse social groups, and even, among student users, cause a marked drop in academic performance (Truel & Serenco, 2012).

However, gender is the only significant demographic variable affecting social media use, as there are some differences between use by men and women. Women are more likely than men to have a personal profile on Facebook, but men are more likely than women to sustain a profile on LinkedIn (Lenhart et al., 2010). Furthermore, women were four to five times more likely than men to use social networking sites (Tufekci, 2010). Moreover, Sheldon (2010) found that overall women were more likely to use social media for maintaining relationships with family and friends, passing time, and entertainment, but men were more likely to use social media to meet new people. College women were also more likely than men to use the internet for relational communication, such as contacts with friends, family, and romantic partners (Baym, Zhang, Kunkel, Ledbetter & Mei-Chen, 2007). Educational experience of men and women seemed to play a factor in social media use as well. Men and women were more likely to use social network sites frequently if they had college experience (Lenhart et al., 2010).

Gender has been found to occupy a special place in understanding people's decisions in the adoption and use of new technologies (Volkovich et al., 2014). Few research on the gender differences in usage patterns of Social Networking Sites (SNS) highlighted that the male gender used social networking sites for networking, making new friends, and seeking out potential dates and playing games; while female gender used it for relationship maintenance (Rousseau & Puttaraju, 2014) and posting public message (Muscanell, 2012). Another related study averred that females used Social Networking Sites predominantly to look for old friends and keep in touch with the existing ones while, at the same time, hiding their identities and personal information for privacy purposes (Mazman & Usluel, 2011).

In contrast of having positive effects, researchers like Shabnoor & Tajinder (2016) and Akram (2018) revealed the negative influence of social media such as lack of proper time management, a source of distraction, exposure to inappropriate content, low academic achievement etc. on students and teenagers wellness. In addition, students start living in the virtual world of social media which leads to decrease in their physical contact with other persons. However, some students are so addicted to the social media that they start describing their daily activities on social media sites and also check their profile regularly so as to have a sense of belonging to the virtual and trending world. Although there are many social media sites and platforms around the globe, the researcher will be focusing his attention on three (Facebook, Whatsapp and Instagram) which are commonly used by university students in Nigeria and the world at large.

In view of this, it becomes glaring that excessive social media usage is becoming a serious issue among university student which is in turn affecting their academic performance as well as their interpersonal relationships. Therefore if proper measures are not taken, students in the universities will continually perform low academically because of their excessive usage of the social media. Based on this background, this study will assess the effect of self-management technique in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students in southern Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria today including Anambra State, many students are performing badly academically. This however could be due to their excessive usage of the social media, which makes them no longer participate effectively in classroom activities, and in turn affect their interpersonal relationship with other students. Apparently, the failure rate of Nigerian students as consistently been recorded in entrance examinations like the JAMB and POST UTME makes it a worrisome situation. For instance, of the 9,996 candidates who sat for the post UTME entrance examinations into the Federal University of Technology Akure in 2015, 5698 failed to meet the 50% cut off mark and therefore not given admission (Oluwole, 2015). This is such that schools are gradually losing their reputation which could likely result in loss of academic and social confidence in the students. More so, when these students fail to gain admission into the higher institution, they could loose interest in education and may involve themselves in societal crimes such as drug abuse, stealing, engaging in cyber crime and some may turn out to become street rascals.

In view of the above, parental intervention have not been sufficient in checkmating and controlling excessive use of social media sites by these students. Teachers and guidance counsellors assigned to these schools, who are trained to handle students educational, vocational, personal and social problems do not make enough impact in correcting the students social media addictive behaviours because of limited time during school hours. Against this, it becomes necessary to find a more effective way to manage and control social media addictive use by these students. Therefore, this study seeks to determine the effects of self management technique in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students in southern Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effect of self management technique in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students in southern Nigeria. Specifically, the study tends to determine the;

1. Effect of self-management technique on excessive social media usage of federal university students when compared to those in the conventional counseling group using their pre-test and post-test scores.
2. Effectiveness of self-management technique on excessive social media usage of male and female federal university students using their pre-test and post-test scores.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of self-management technique on excessive social media usage of federal university students when compared to those in the conventional counseling group using their post-test scores.
2. There is no significant difference in effectiveness of self-management technique on excessive social media usage of male and female federal university students using their post-test scores.

Method

This study was delimited to three most commonly used social media sites by university students which are Facebook, Instagram and Whatsapp. The independent variable is the self-management technique, while excessive social media usage is the dependent variable, in the same vein, gender was considered in the study. The design to be adopted for the study is a quasi experimental research design. Specifically, the study adopted a pretest-posttest non randomised control group. This is because subjects were not randomly assigned to groups and the experiment was carried out outside the laboratory. According to Nworgu (2015), quasi experimental study does not allow for randomization of subjects to experimental and control groups. Quasi experimental design might allow the researcher to have control over assigning subjects to the treatment condition by using some criteria other than random assignment (e.g., a cut-off score) to determine which participant receives the treatment. The study was carried out in the Southern Nigeria. The population of the study was 928 university students while 65 students were sampled for the study using SMD.

The instrument for data collection which the researchers adapted for the study is the Social Media Disorder (SMD) scale. It is a standardized instrument developed by Eijnden, Lemmen & Valkenburg (2016), in Armsterdam, Neitherland. The SMD was scales thus; NONE; 0 – 22.35 points, MODERATE; 22.5 – 37.35 points; an average online user who surfs the web a bit too long and is beginning to have little issues over usage, WORRISOME; 37.5 – 52.35 point; experiencing frequent problems because of the social media and SEVERE; 52.5 – 60 points; internet usage is causing significant problems. Should evaluate the impact of social media and address the problems directly. The researchers adapted the SMD instrument for the study. Reliability coefficient of the instrument was established to be 0.87 which indicated that internal consistency of the test score was good based on the tetrachoric correlation matrix. There were other reliability tested and the total information was highest at $\Theta = 1.68$ (corresponding to endorsement of ± 6 criteria), which indicates that test scores were most reliable at this value. The researchers with the help of researcher assistants collected the data. They both distributed the instrument to the students and properly guided them on how to respond to the questions on it. When the students finished answering the questions on the instrument, the researcher collected them back from the students and analyzed. The Social Media Disorder (SMD) scale was used as pre - test, after which the actual treatment was done on the experimental and control groups for six weeks. The Social Media Disorder (SMD) scale was then re-administered to the students as post-test to determine the level of change the treatment had on the students in both the experimental and control groups.

The completed standardized instruments on Social Media Disorder (SMD) scale was scored according to the scoring instruction on the SMD manual. The data collected from the instrument was organized thus; Scores 37.5 - 60 = High social media usage and 0 - 37.5 = Low social media usage. Mean score was used to answer the research questions while hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance with Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest social media usage mean scores of students treated with SMT and those treated with conventional counselling

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Self-management Tech.	43	54.02	28.42	25.6	
Control	22	53.45	42.36	11.09	Effective

Table 1 reveals that the students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 54.02 and posttest mean score of 28.42 with lost mean 25.6 in their social media usage scores, while those in the control group who were trained with conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 53.45 and posttest mean score of 42.36 with lost mean 11.09. With posttest mean score of 28.42 which is below 37.5 norm, self-management technique is effective in reducing students' excessive usage of social media.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest social media mean scores of male and female students treated with SMT

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Male	19	54.32	29.16	25.16	
Female	24	53.79	27.93	25.96	More effective

In table 2 it was observed that the male students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 54.32 and posttest mean score of 29.16 with lost mean 25.16 in their social media usage scores, while the female students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 53.79 and posttest mean score of 27.93 with lost mean 25.96 in their social media usage scores. Self-management technique is more effective in reducing female students' excessive usage of social media.

Table 3: ANCOVA on the effect of self-management technique on excessive social media usage of students compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their posttest scores

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	2864.765	2	1432.383			
Intercept	173.230	1	173.230			
Pretest	34.5681	34.568				
Treatment methods	2608.573	1	2608.573	104.28	0.000	S
Error	1550.988	62	25.016			
Total	75796.000	65				
Corrected Total	4415.754	64				

In table 3, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 64df denominator, the calculated F is 104.28 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effect of self-management technique in reducing students' usage of social media is significant.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the effectiveness of self-management technique on usage of social media of male and female students using their posttest scores.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
---------------------	----	----	----	--------	--------	----------

Corrected Model	59.707	2	29.854		
Intercept	126.353	1	126.353		
Pretest	41.102	1	41.102		
Gender	29.310	1	29.310	0.930	.341 NS
Error	1260.758	40	31.519		
Total	36048.000	43			
Corrected Total	1320.465	42			

Table 4 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 42df denominator, the calculated F is 0.93 with Pvalue of 0.341 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is accepted. So, there is no significant difference in the effectiveness of self-management technique on excessive usage of social media of male and female students.

Discussion

The result of the study shows that self management technique is effective in reducing the excessive social media usage behaviour of federal university students. The finding is in line with the study carried out by Asad, Muhammad, Abdul, Hassan and Ehsan (2019) on evaluating the effects of social networking sites addiction, task distraction, and self-management on university student nurses' performance. In this study, they stated that that self-management mediates the relationship between SNSs addiction and students performance, and that self-management reduces the negative impact of SNSs addiction on university student nurses' performance. This simply means that those students that were determined to monitor and observe their social media related activities online as well as the amount of time they spend on the social media site were able to control themselves so they do not get addicted. The findings also corresponds with Brevers and Turel (2019) who carried out a study on the techniques for self-managing social media use in preventing social media addiction symptoms among college students in the United States. Brevers and Turel revealed through the study that self-management techniques are significant in reducing social media addiction symptoms. Similarly, Oguzie, Obi and Nnadi (2019) reported that self-management technique is effective in reducing maladaptive behaviours among students.

The result also showed that self management technique is more significant in reducing excessive social media usage of female students. However, the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for gender as its main effect in table 4 showed that there was no significant difference in the effectiveness of self-management technique on excessive usage of social media of male and female students. This explains that gender is not really a significant factor in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students. The finding agrees with an online survey carried out by Brevers and Turel (2019) on the techniques for self-managing social media use in preventing social media addiction symptoms among college students in the United States. The authors confirmed that self-management technique such as self-control or self regulation enables students reduce their addiction to the social media. The study then revealed that self-management strategy is more significant in preventing social media addiction symptoms of the female students.

Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have implications on the students with excessive social media usage behaviour, teachers, parents, counsellors, future researchers and the society at large. The study brings to knowledge how effective self management is in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students. This means that students can manage and reduce those social media related activities that make them spend so much time of social media sites to the point that it begins to negatively affect their academic performance as well as interpersonal relationships with fellow students and peers.

The findings of this study will also improve classroom teaching and learning activities as the teachers and counsellors will have students who are much more attentive and also partake effectively in classroom activities and this will make teaching a lot easier for the teacher. This study will also help parents be exposed to the dangers of excessive social media usage for their children and the strategies that will help them manage this maladaptive behaviour of their children.

Finally, the study has great implication on the society. The society at large can experience less cyber crime and other social vices which these young ones learn on the internet on various social media platforms. Self management technique will help the students with excessive social media usage behaviour experience a reasonable level of self-instruction, self-motivation, self-monitoring, self-reinforcement and a healthy sense of self-discipline, thereby avoiding that anti-social behaviour that is harmful to the society.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated a lot of positive effect that self management technique has in managing and reducing excessive social media use which were confirmed by previous research works carried out on students behaviours in relation to excessive or problematic use of the social media. Conclusion drawn from the study strongly implied that self management technique was effective in reducing excessive social media usage among federal university students. Self management technique was more effective in reducing female students excessive usage of the social media as well as second year students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. Self-management strategies and techniques should be adopted by students to help them monitor and observe their social media usage which would enable them control themselves when their online presence and activities are becoming problematic. This intervention will help students focus more on academic activities and be able to achieve academic excellence rather than while away most of their time on social media networks.
2. Having seen that self management technique can help in reducing excessive social media usage, counselling intervention for students should be strengthened. Academic counsellors through workshops and seminars can expose students to various self-management techniques like self-monitoring, self-instruction etc. which students can equip themselves with to be able to manage or reduce their excessive usage of the social media. Through this intervention, students will begin to perform better academically as well as in their interpersonal relationships with fellow students because they are able to reorganize their social media usage through self- management techniques.

REFERENCES

- Ahad, A.D. & Lim, S. (2014). Convenience or nuisance? The 'WhatsApp' dilemma. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 155, 189-196.
- Andreassen, C.S. & Pallesen, S. (2014). Social network site addiction-an overview. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 20, 4053-4061.
- Baym, N.K., Zhang, Y.B., Kunkel, A., Ledbetter, A. & Mei-Chen, L. (2007). Relational quality and media use in interpersonal relationships. *New Media & Society*, 9(5), 735-752.
- Cabral, J. (2011). Is Generation 1 addicted to social networks: Why do we use facebook? *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 27(4); 1337-1343.
- Clark, W., Logan, K., Luckin, R., Mee, A. & Oliver, M. (2009). Beyond web 2.0: mapping the technology landscapes of young learners. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 25(1), 56-69.
- Ghulam, S., Yousef, M. & Syed, M. (2014). The impact of social media on youth: A case study of Bahawalpur City. *Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 3(4). 1732-1769.
- Griffitts, M .D., Kuss, D.J. & Demetrovics, Z. (2014). Social networking addiction: An overview of preliminary findings. *Journal of Behavioural Addictions Criteria, Evidence and Treatment*, 5, 19-41.
- Lenhart, A., Purcell, K., Smith, A. & Zickuhr, K. (2010). *Social media and young adults*. Chicago: Pew Internet & American Life Research Center.
- Mazman, S.G., & Usluel, Y.K. (2011). Gender differences in using social networks. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 10(2), 133-139.
- Meishar-Tal, H., Kurtz, G. & Pieterse, E. (2012). Facebook groups as LMS: A case study. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 13(4), 33-48.

- Muscanell, N. & Guadagno, R. (2012). Make new friends or keep the old: Gender and personality differences in social networking use. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 28, 107-112.
- Oguzie, A.E., Obi, J.S.C. & Nnadi, G.C. (2019). Effect of self-management technique on shyness among secondary school students in Imo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 7(5), 241-252.
- Pamnkaghlian, V.M. (2011). The brief guide to school networking addiction: A scientific no man's land? *Brain Blogger*: Retrieved on January 7, 2011, from <http://brainblogger.com/social-network-additiona-a-scientific-no-mas-land>.
- Rousseau, J.S & Puttaraju, K. (2014). A Study of Gender Differential Factors in the uses of Social Networking Sites. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Innovation*, 3(2), 31-40.
- Shabnoor, S. & Tajinder, S. (2016). Social media and its impact with positive and negative aspects. *International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research*, 5(2); 71-75.
- Sheldon, P. (2010). Student favorite: Facebook and motives for its use. *Southwestern Mass Communication Journal*, 23(2), 39-53.
- Tufekci, Z. (2010). Grooming, gossip, facebook, and myspace. *Journal of Information, Communication and Society*, 11(4), 544-56.
- Turel, O., & Serenko, A. (2012). The benefits and dangers of enjoyment with social networking websites. *European Journal of Information System*, 21(5), 12-28.
- Volkovich, Y., Laniado, D., Kappler, K.E & Kantentbrunner, A. (2014). Gender Patterns in a large online social network. Available at http://www.dtic.upf.edu/~akalten/volkovich_etalSocInfo2014.pdf
- Wu, A.M., Cheung, V.I., Ku, L. & Hung, E.P. (2013). Psychological risk factors of addiction to social networking sites among Chinese smart phone users. *Journal of Behavioural Addictions*, 2(3), 6-160.